

OSCAR

Open Science Clusters' Action
for Research & Society

D4.3 - Exploitation Plan

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EC Project Officer	Enrico Pellizzari

<i>Date</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Partner</i>	<i>Role</i>
Responsible partner:	Nicoletta Carboni	CERIC-ERIC	WP4 Co-lead
Contributor 1	Giovanni Lamanna	CNRS	OSCARS project coordinator
Contributor 2	Friederike Schmidt-Tremmel	Trust-IT	OSCARS project manager, WP4 Co-lead
Contributor 3	Rob Carrillo	Trust-IT	WP4 Co-lead
Contributor 4	Jordi Bodega Sempere	ESRF	WP1 Co-lead
Contributor 5	Gary Saunders	EATRIS ERIC	WP1 Co-lead
Contributor 6	Sally Chambers	DARIAH ERIC	WP2 Co-lead
Contributor 7	Paul Millar	DESY	WP2 Co-lead
Contributor 8	Romain David	ERINHA	WP3 Co-lead
Contributor 9	Anca Hienola	FMI	WP3 Co-lead
Contributor 10	Maud Coppel	CNRS	WP4 contributor
Contributor 11	Justine Thomas	CNRS	WP4 contributor
Contributor 12	Andreas Petzold	FZ Jülich	Science Cluster Board member
Contributor 13	Jonathan Ewbank	ERINHA	Science Cluster Board member
Contributor 14	Bonnie Wolff-Boenisch	CESSDA ERIC	Science Cluster Board member

DELIVERABLE ABSTRACT

Deliverable 4.3 gives an overview of the planned communication activities and those that have already been implemented in the first half year of OSCARS. It also sets out the plan for further communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. In addition, it provides the guidelines to:

- Communicate the scope, objectives and activities of the project, by defining the main project's target audiences, key messages and media used according to the specific communication objectives and needs, as well as to the type of output to be achieved.
- Disseminate the key results of OSCARS and of the Open Science projects and services funded through the cascading-grant Open Calls to key stakeholders, by defining the planned actions and the channels and tools to be deployed for the scope;
- Exploit the results of OSCARS and the Open Science projects and services funded via the OSCARS Open Calls, by defining how they are expected to be concretely used even after the project's end.

Throughout the project, partners will promote its activities, targeting specific key groups and ensuring that the results of OSCARS' consolidation activities and the outcomes of the Open Science projects and services are effectively communicated and disseminated to the widest number of stakeholders by using the appropriate channels and tools, based on this document.

The communication plan has already been implemented since the start of the project, whereas dissemination and exploitation actions will be implemented as soon as the first results will be available.

Appropriate actions, tools and target groups will be addressed according to the project's stage of implementation, linking the communication, dissemination and exploitation actions with the tasks in progress.

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Executive summary

OSCARS - Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society - is a four-year Horizon Europe project, which aims to foster the uptake of Open Science in Europe by consolidating the achievements of world-class European research infrastructures (RIs) in the ESFRI roadmap and beyond into lasting interdisciplinary FAIR data services and working practices. The project will strengthen the role of the Science Clusters in the ERA by developing domain-based Competence Centres and by fostering the implementation of Open Science projects and services funded through a cascading grant mechanism.

The purpose of this document is to outline OSCARS' specific communication, dissemination and exploitation actions, to maximise the impact of the project and to ensure its success both during its 48 months duration, and after its completion.

In chapters 2 and 3, the project's objectives and its main communication and dissemination goals are described. These include the active support of the key activities of the project, both from the consolidation activities of the Science Clusters' achievements in the previous Horizon 2020 projects, and from the cascading-grant Open Science projects and services plus their results.

Target audiences, key messages and communication and dissemination channels and tools have been identified and are described in detail in chapters 4, 5 and 6.

Internal communication is the focus of chapter 7, with the list and description of the tools set up to ensure that all OSCARS members are up to date about the project's progress and achievements, and enabled to ensure a proper communication flow between the different work packages.

Chapters 8 and 9 showcase the communication and dissemination plans for both the consolidation activities and the Open Calls.

These include the setup and population of the project's website and the grants' platform, the deployment of the digital communication tools of the project, communication and dissemination campaigns, the organisation and attendance of conferences, workshops, webinars and events, the production of audio-visual resources for training and for disseminating the results of OSCARS and the Open Science projects and services, the production of use cases and science demonstrators, branded communication materials, and other relevant content.

The exploitation plan includes the expected key-exploitable results, to be updated in a later stage of the project, once the first results from the Science Clusters' consolidation activities and the Open Science projects and services will be available.

Finally, the last chapter briefly describes the resources committed in OSCARS' WP4, for the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities described in the previous chapters.

1. Introduction

It is crucial that communication starts right from the beginning of the project, to inform, promote and communicate the project's activities and results. Strategic thinking and planning what messages need to be conveyed, where, when and how, is vital for its success.

Dissemination comes at a later stage, to make knowledge and results publicly available, in particular to the project's target audiences (see table 3), who can learn and benefit from the results, whereas exploitation implies making concrete use of results for commercial, societal and political purposes, with actions addressing those who can take the results forward, or invest in them.

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plans of the OSCARS project are thus meant to provide guidelines to properly reach these goals, by defining the main project's target audiences, key messages and media used according to the specific communication, dissemination and exploitation objectives and needs, as well as to the type of output to be achieved.

Throughout the project, partners will promote both its planned consolidation activities, and the results of the Open Science projects and services funded via the OSCARS Open Calls, targeting specific key groups and ensuring that results are effectively communicated and disseminated to the widest number of stakeholders by using the appropriate channels and tools, based on the indications and plans found in this document.

Appropriate actions, tools and target groups will be addressed, according to the project's stage of implementation, linking the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities with the task in progress.

The following documents have been used as a basis for this deliverable, and will be deployed as useful resources for its implementation for the whole duration of the project:

- [INFOGRAPHICS] Communication, dissemination & exploitation what is the difference and why they all matter
<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/58ad3394-0a63-11ee-b12e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-287940279>
- [WEBSITE] European Research Executive Agency guidelines about “Communicating about your EU-funded project”:
https://rea.ec.europa.eu/communicating-about-your-eu-funded-project_en
- [WEBSITE] European Research Executive Agency guidelines (including list and links to free of charge dissemination services) about “Horizon Europe Dissemination and Exploitation”:
https://rea.ec.europa.eu/dissemination-and-exploitation_en
- [WEBINAR] Dissemination and Exploitation in Horizon Europe:
<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/other/event210609.htm>

- [EC REGULATIONS] Horizon Europe Regulation 2021/695, Article 39 - Exploitation and dissemination, and Article 51: Information, communication, publicity and dissemination and exploitation: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2021/695/oj>
- [EC DOCUMENTS] AGA - Annotated Grant Agreement, Annex 5, 7. Exploitation of results: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf

Based on these, the project will implement a combined communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy, with the aim of raising awareness among different target groups as presented in table 3, about the results of the consolidation activities, and of the Open Science projects and services, highlighting the benefits that the project actions bring to the research communities in the Science Clusters and beyond, while ensuring EU visibility by a correct implementation of the guidelines as defined in the key background documents listed above. The final goal is to foster the uptake of Open Science by the scientific communities across and beyond the Science Clusters, as well as by citizen scientists, industry, and more.

Effective communication also means an increased coordination and networking among the members of OSCARS (internal communication), and between them and the other EOSC projects, initiatives and stakeholders, towards a coordinated and harmonised implementation of the EOSC and the adoption of Open Research and Open Science practices by researchers across Europe.

This document therefore outlines communication objectives, key messages, target audiences, activities, tools and resources for facilitating the exchange and dissemination of information, both for internal and external communication means. The tools deployed for this purpose include emails, the project website, an intranet and online repositories for partners, social networks, print materials, press articles, e-newsletters, workshops, and other dissemination and networking events. Finally, specific actions will be put in place to enable the transferability of the results to other public and private entities and potential stakeholders in different geographical areas.

2. Description, objectives and partners of the project

OSCARS - Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society - is a four-year Horizon Europe project, which aims to foster the uptake of Open Science in Europe by consolidating the achievements of world-class European research infrastructures (RIs) in the ESFRI roadmap and beyond into lasting interdisciplinary FAIR data services and working practices. The project will strengthen the role of the Science Clusters (SCs) in the ERA by developing domain-based Competence Centres and by providing Composable Open Data and Analysis Services (CODAS) accessible via Virtual Research Environments (VREs), while fostering the implementation of Open Science projects and services funded through a cascading grant mechanism.

In particular OSCARS' objectives are to:

1. Consolidate achievements from the five H2020 INFRA-EOSC-2018-01-04 projects into lasting interdisciplinary services and working practices towards:
 - More cohesion;
 - Leveraging **cross-domain approach** and **cooperation with e-infrastructures**;
 - **Cross-fertilisation** for shared solutions of key services for researchers in all domains;
 - Cooperating and supporting the **EOSC partnership**.

2. Lead the involvement of a broad range of research communities in Open Research (EOSC) via the development of new Open Science projects/services to drive the uptake of FAIR-data-intensive research throughout the ERA by:
 - Contributing to a **data space for science, research and innovation**, integrated into the other data spaces described in the European Strategy for Data.
 - Pursuing the creation of **pan-European research-enabling value-added services**;
 - Fostering the **coordination** of national activities, European RIs and the scientific community at large, including the long tail of science;
 - Fostering **interdisciplinarity** for achieving challenging new science pathways.

With the OSCARS work programme and deliverables, the Science Clusters intend to consolidate their role as thematic EU nodes for 'Open Research'. They will establish and operate Competence Centres and VREs fostering the alignment of practices in scientific data analysis. The cascading grant action is aimed at supporting researchers in uptaking FAIR data analysis and providing a series of valuable scientific demonstrators for such a role of the SCs and for the benefit of the scientific impact of EOSC.

Table 1. OSCARS partners and social media channels

OSCARS Partners					
N.	Partner	Abbreviation	Country	X (Twitter)	Linkedin
1	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique CNRS	CNRS-LAPP	France	@LAPPCNRS	https://www.linkedin.com/company/lapp-cnrs/
2	Organisation Européenne pour la Recherche Nucléaire	CERN	Switzerland	@CERN	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cern/
3	Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH	FZJ	Germany	@fz_juelich	https://www.linkedin.com/company/forschungszentrum-julich
4	e-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research	Lifewatch ERIC	Spain	@LifeWatchERIC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/lifewatch-eric/
5	Ilmatieteen Laitos	FMI	Finland	@meteorologit	https://www.linkedin.com/company/finnish-meteorological-institute/
6	European Molecular Biology Laboratory	ELIXIR	Germany	@ELIXIREurope	https://www.linkedin.com/company/elixir-europe/
7	European infrastructure for translational medicine - ERIC	EATRIS ERIC	The Netherlands	@EatrisEric	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eatris-eric/
8	European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents	ERINHA	Belgium	@ERINHA_RI	https://www.linkedin.com/company/erinha/
9	European Synchrotron Radiation Facility	ESRF	France	@esrfsynchrotron	https://www.linkedin.com/company/esrf-european-radiation-synchrotron-facility/
10	Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY	DESY	Germany	@desynews	https://www.linkedin.com/company/desy/
11	Central European Research Infrastructure Consortium - ERIC	CERIC-ERIC	Italy	@CERICnews	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ceric-eric/
12	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure - ERIC	CLARIN ERIC	The Netherlands	@CLARINERIC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/clarin-eric/
13	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives - ERIC	CESSDA ERIC	Norway	@CESSDA_Data	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cessda/
14	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities ERIC	DARIAH ERIC	France	@DARIAHeu	https://www.linkedin.com/company/dariah-eric/
15	Trust-IT SRL	Trust-IT	Italy	@TrustITServices	https://www.linkedin.com/company/trust-it-services/

3. OSCARS' Communication and Dissemination Objectives

OSCARS will dedicate resources for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation, to support project's objectives by providing tools and actions to increase the visibility and favour the exploitation of project's outputs, and of the results of both the consolidation activities and the Open Science projects and services funded through the project.

3.1 Internal Communication

Internal communication activities aim to:

- **Ensure a smooth and effective exchange within the project partnership and the Science Clusters**, guaranteeing a proper flow of information throughout the different bodies of the management structure by following the principles of cooperation and transparency, and by respecting the rules on confidentiality.
- **Strengthen project partners' and the Science Clusters' coordination and networking by means of internal communications tools** fully dedicated to the project and its partners, and by providing the proper online and offline environment for open discussions of common challenges and the exchange of best practices.

Tools: Periodical meetings within and across WPs, Executive Board (EoB) meetings, Science Cluster Board (SCB) meetings, Annual Project Meetings (AGMs), project internal newsletter, internal repositories, mailing lists, co-working virtual platforms (i.e., Slack, Skype, Google Drive / Google docs and spreadsheets, repositories (CNRS' box.in2p3.fr and shared calendars).

With respect to the two core focuses of the project - the consolidation activities and the cascading-grant Open Calls - the related communication and dissemination objectives are presented in the following sections.

3.2 Consolidation Activities

Key communication objectives with respect to OSCARS' consolidation activities are:

- **[COMMUNICATION]** Convey clear messages, scope and progress of the project consolidation activities among relevant stakeholders to to increase the visibility of OSCARS¹.

¹ All partners involved in the project ensure that all their bodies and partners are well informed about the project's progress and that they are actively involved in its activities, by internally adopting and implementing their own communication guidelines.

- **[COMMUNICATION]** Promoting awareness, involvement, and activity of CCCs within the scientific community at large, towards an increase of the knowledge about the Community-based Competence Centres (CCC) across all domains.
- **[DISSEMINATION]** Increase the awareness and knowledge among the research communities across and beyond the Science Clusters, about the work of OSCARS, stimulating access to and collaboration with the CCCs,.
- **[COMMUNICATION and DISSEMINATION]** Promoting and fostering the use and further development of Composable Open Data and Analysis Services (CODAS) across all domains.
- **[DISSEMINATION]** Promote access to, and stimulate use of Virtual Research Environments (VREs) and FAIR data services and tools among research communities from all domains, in and beyond the Science Clusters, for their use in an Open Science and Open Research approach.
- **[COMMUNICATION and DISSEMINATION]** Foster cooperation with international Fora, and with EOSC- and RI development-related projects by maintaining frequent exchanges and updates on the project progress and on the milestones achieved, to network, build and maintain a federation of data and services across clusters and RIs, and to share competences, knowledge and best practices on FAIR data, Open Science and data management practices.
- **[DISSEMINATION and EXPLOITATION]** Disseminate the project's results by making OSCARS' results - milestones, deliverables, peer-reviewed publications, software, services and service/data catalogues, use cases and science demonstrators - easily accessible and publicly available, to stimulate the uptake of Open Science and Open Research by researchers from all domains, citizen scientists, industry, and more, for them to further contribute to a data space for science, research and innovation.
- **[EXPLOITATION]** Promote the adoption of FAIR data and Open Science practices through CCCs, through the publication of white papers, the setup of CCC-specific registries including CCCs' members (RIs staff, IT professionals, data stewards, and more).
- **[EXPLOITATION]** Stimulate the use and further exploitation of CODAS through the publication of CODAS use cases and demonstrators.
- **[EXPLOITATION]** Support cross-disciplinary collaboration across the Science Clusters, leveraging on the experience and expertise of the CCCs to foster research excellence through training and knowledge transfer.

3.3 Cascading-grant Open Calls for Open Science Projects and Services

- **[COMMUNICATION]** Inform the research communities within, across and beyond the Science Clusters about the OSCARS Open Calls for Open Science projects and services, and attract potential applicants, through conferences and other events, by setting up all the tools needed for the scope (grants' platform, project's website, social media accounts, newsletters, etc.), and by populating them with useful content (information about the Open Calls, FAQs, glossary, video, webinars' recordings, examples of Open Science projects, presentations, white papers and other resources, social media posts, etc.).
- **[COMMUNICATION]** Increase the knowledge across the research communities in all domains, as well as among funding agencies and policymakers, about the cascading-grant mechanism (calls' objectives, funding available, selection/evaluation criteria, etc.) applied in the frame of OSCARS, and about the progress of the Open Science projects being implemented.
- **[DISSEMINATION and EXPLOITATION]** Disseminate the results of the successful Open Science projects and services to key stakeholders (RIs, scientists across all domains, industry, the EC and other funding bodies at the regional and national level), through a combination of means (digital communication - social media, digital brochures, webinars, videos, etc., Open Science ambassadors invited to present at OSCARS-related events, publication of use cases, science demonstrators, etc.), to maximise their impact and foster the uptake of Open Science and Open Research by researchers from all domains, in and beyond the Science Clusters.
- **[EXPLOITATION]** Ensure the OSCARS' legacy by making available to stakeholders after the end of the project, the training material on FAIR data and Open Science, as well as the relevant (meta-)data, services, software and tools, and the documentation produced in the frame of the Open Science projects.

Table 2. List of expected changes that the project aims to promote, and possible KPIs (to be updated in a later stage of the project's implementation)

N.	EXPECTED CHANGE	ACTIONS	TARGET	KPI
1	Higher number of scientists uptaking Open Science and Open Research, with a consequent increased awareness of the benefits of Open Science and Open Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promotion of the OSCARS Open Calls to research communities from all domains (in and beyond the SCs). - Dissemination of the results of the OS projects funded. - Collect and release mentorship resources from the SCs. - Support the promotion of use case / science demonstrators. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (e-)Research Infrastructures - Researchers - Industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of funded Open Science projects - No. of dissemination articles published - No. of dissemination events attended - No. of invited talks
3	Operation of the CCCs and use by the research communities in the SCs for training and knowledge transfer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Setup of the CCCs - Promotion of the CCCs and their services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research communities from all domains - Trainers - RIs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of training resources available - No. of cross-disciplinary collaborations fostered by the CCCs
4	Increased awareness of the FAIR data practices, hands-on experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creation and promotion of training material - Organisation of workshops, webinars, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Young researchers of targeted scientific communities - Data stewards / managers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of participants - Feedback forms
5	Setup and increased awareness of Science Clusters' CODAS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continuous development and maintenance of CODAS in and across the SCs. - Presentation of CODAS to research communities in all domains. - Promotion of the FAIR data services, software and tools through all available channels, events and platforms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers / Data stewards - Other EOSC projects / initiatives - (e-)RIs - EC, other funding agencies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of CODAS available

6	Research reproducibility increase	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standardised metadata schemas, technical infrastructure to support reproducibility, give researchers access to data, software and workflows. - Promotion of the OSCARS Open Calls highlighting the possibility to present cross-domain projects. - Organisation of dedicated workshops and actions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data Stewards - Researchers - Train-the-trainers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of implemented FAIR-enabling resources supporting reproducibility - No. of different institutes funded in the Open Calls to highlight diversity of institutions participating and multi-domain collaborations - No. of workshop and online training / actions
7	Increased level of cooperation among the SCs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bi-weekly / monthly meetings of the Science Cluster Board. - Consolidation activities in WP1, WP2, WP3 and bi-weekly joint meetings of all WPs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RIs in the Science Clusters - Researchers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of multi-domain collaborations in the frame of OSCARS
8	Increased no. of OSCARS-related publications linking to data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creation of services to link to existing publications and underlined experiment data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers - Librarians 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of publications linking to data DOIs/cite - Impact scores - No. of publications about Data Management with OSCARS' involvement
9	Increased use of developed services in combination with the services in the EOSC.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contribution of resources, data services, tools and software, to the EOSC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers - RIs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of combinations between high-level services and core services in EOSC

4. Target Audiences

Communication and dissemination need to be customised and adapted to the different target groups and stakeholders identified in the project.

The table below provides a classification of key target audiences to be considered when pursuing specific communication objectives, in order to be able to plan well in advance the adaptation of messages, tools and actions according to the background, expectations and practices of each group.

Table 3. List of the OSCARS target groups of internal / external communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

INTERNAL COMMUNICATION – TARGET GROUPS
Project Partners
Project bodies (Executive Board, Science Cluster Board, Coordinator, WP leaders and contributors)
EC Project Officer
EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION – TARGET GROUPS
Research communities within and beyond the Science Clusters (incl. user communities and organisations)
(e-)Research Infrastructures, public and private research institutes
Universities and university alliances (e.g., GUILD, EUTOPIA, LERU, CELSA)
Cluster-specific scientific networks
IT staff, engineers, developers at RIs
NCPs for RIs
Data managers, data stewards
Service providers
Common European Data Spaces
Industry representatives
Other EOSC projects (Skills4EOSC, EOSC Beyond, EOSC Focus, FAIR Impact etc.), Task Forces and initiatives (e.g., EOSC-A)
Data initiatives (RDA, CODATA, etc.)
Communities of European RIs, e.g., ESFRI – European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures, ERIC Forum
EC DG RTD – Research and Innovation
EC DG Connect
National Ministries for science and research
Other policy makers at the regional, national and European level
Citizen scientists
Media and general public
EXPLOITATION
Research communities across and beyond the Science Clusters, in both academia and industry
Service providers
(e-)RIs
EU governing bodies and European Commission – all relevant DGs
Citizen scientists
Data managers, data stewards, data scientists
Service providers
Data initiatives and fora (RDA, CODATA, WDS etc.)

5. Key Messages

This paragraph provides some general guidelines to describe OSCARS to its key target audiences.

5.1 Target-driven key messages

Target-driven key messages	
TARGET AUDIENCE	CONTENT
<p>Researchers</p>	<p>CONSOLIDATION ACTIVITIES OSCARS will enhance community-based science services and data sources, in order to support new and novel scientific research through their combined use. It will also provide highly composable research-enabling exemplar demonstrators, as well as data processing and management solutions for researchers across all scientific domains.</p> <p>OPEN CALLS OSCARS strives to foster the involvement of a broad range of research communities in EOSC by launching two Open Calls (total worth ~16 million Euro) for the development of innovative Open Science projects and services, that together will drive the uptake of FAIR-data-intensive research throughout the European Research Area (ERA). Open Science projects are scientific research projects, citizen science projects, or proposals to develop services or networks, in the scientific disciplines covered by, and beyond the Science Clusters. Their objective is to make (meta)data, software, tools and/or workflows FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and available to fellow researchers and the general public, to facilitate accessibility and reuse by the scientific community at large, citizen scientists, industry, and more. Projects can be proposed in the field of any of the SCs and beyond, by any researcher or group of researchers, and will be funded through a cascading grant mechanism.</p>
<p>(e-)RIs</p>	<p>OSCARS brings together world-class European RIs from the ESFRI roadmap and beyond, with the ultimate goal of fostering the uptake of Open Science in Europe across scientific disciplines and communities. To increase data FAIRness, OSCARS will further develop a FAIR-compliant certification scheme for research data and community-based science platforms, which might be used in combination with the services of the EOSC EU Node. It will provide access to FAIR data services, data sources, guidelines and training, but also to highly composable research-enabling services, as well as data processing and management solutions. The concept of Cluster based Open Science Competence Centres will be deployed to leverage the specific achievements and competences of each cluster, addressing each scientific community's culture and needs, while at the same time strengthening intra-cluster collaboration by sharing best practices and jointly developing common strategies.</p>
<p>Data managers / Data stewards</p>	<p>OSCARS will develop a registry of stakeholders, a dashboard and a series of actions to further widen the uptake of Open Science, exploring and deploying strategies to involve smaller or less structured communities, providing training, support material and methods, and coaching. This will make sure that services developed are assessed against their usefulness, usability, functionality and performance, by users from various fields of science.</p>
<p>EC, EC DG RTD, DG Connect and policymakers</p>	<p>OSCARS and the Science Clusters will consolidate their role as thematic EOSC EU nodes for 'Open Research', and will establish and operate Competence Centres and virtual research environments fostering the alignment of practices in scientific data analysis.</p>

5.2 Visual and Identity Narratives

The following texts provide a short and effective reference to describe OSCARS and its key goals, objectives and actions. These key messages are aimed at defining the identity of the project in order to simplify and homogenise its communication to major target audiences and stakeholders. Hence, they will be used as a guideline to produce material useful for media in need of information on OSCARS.

The mission statement helps internal stakeholders identify with the project and its goals (*what do we do and why are we doing what we are doing?*) and external audiences identifying the domain of the activity and specificity of the project (*what are they doing and why are they doing it?*).

OSCARS' MISSION

OSCARS - Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society - is a four-year Horizon Europe project, which aims to foster the uptake of Open Science in Europe by consolidating the achievements of world-class European research infrastructures (RIs) in the ESFRI roadmap and beyond, into lasting interdisciplinary FAIR data services and working practices. The project will strengthen the role of the Science Clusters in the ERA by developing domain-based Competence Centres and by fostering the implementation of Open Science projects and services funded through a cascading grant mechanism.

OSCARS' SCOPE and VISION

The Science Clusters consolidate their role as thematic Nodes for Open Research in Europe. Through OSCARS, they will establish and operate scientific community-based Competence Centres and virtual research environments fostering the alignment of practices in scientific Open Data research.

OSCARS helps in finding more commonalities across the Science Clusters, strengthening their cooperation, and fosters scientists from all scientific domains to take up Open Science and make use of the resources in EOSC.

OSCARS' visual identity manual is available [here](#).

5.3 Horizon Europe Rules

Unless the European Commission requests or agrees otherwise, or unless it is impossible, any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment, and major results funded by the grant must:

- Display the EU emblem.
- Include the following texts in all project's materials: "*Funded by the European Union*"
- When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

Moreover, the partners are due to fulfil all the requirements established by the EC in the Grant Agreement and in the [Horizon Europe Online Manual](#).

6. Communication Channels and Tools

The goal of external communication and dissemination is to engage all project stakeholders in fostering the uptake of Open Science in Europe, and to ensure the dissemination of the project outputs and results by all available means.

CERIC-ERIC, Trust-IT and CNRS, in coordination with all the other project partners, will be the key responsible partners for the promotion of the project, its activities, advancements and events, and for the dissemination of its outputs, up to their further exploitation, by using a combination of different communication channels and tools.

Actions taken to pass information to, and interact with stakeholders, will have the following forms:

1. Public project updates via the project's, the Science Clusters' and their partners' websites, newsletters and social media posts, as well as articles and/or press releases about key OSCARS events and achievements.
2. Interaction with multiple stakeholders at the project annual meetings and at specific meetings of the Science Clusters' research and user communities, at scientific and industrial workshops and conferences Europe-wide, at the ICRI conferences, EU presidency's events, EOSC events, etc.
3. Interaction with contact points of the National Ministries:
 - a. At the partners' governing bodies' meetings;
 - b. At events organised by the Ministries;
 - c. By standard contact points of government grant agencies in countries where partners are present.
4. Interaction with other EOSC projects, task forces and initiatives for the coordination and co-development of services.

Customised materials for external communication, dissemination and exploitation of the results will be produced and distributed to inform and raise awareness about project partners' activities, achievements and results among stakeholders and potential beneficiaries listed in Table 3, and to steer further exploitation. The tools proposed by the project to support external communication and dissemination activities are listed below. These are linked to specific activities in the project's work plan, which shall be adopted and continuously updated (at least on a yearly basis) throughout the whole lifecycle of the project:

- Project communication strategy and plan
- Internal communication plan
- Project website
- Science Clusters' websites
- Social media accounts (of OSCARS and its partners)

- Project brochure(s)
- Project newsletters
- Audio-visual material
- Media relations
- Promotional material (rollups, posters, gadgets, etc.)
- Promotional campaigns
- Reporting
- Networking and outreach events
- Scientific and other selected conferences
- Training events and material

Table 4 describes each tool linking it to the relevant partner and to the key performance indicator(s) (KPIs), as well as to the expected delivery timeframe.

Table 4. List of communication tools

Tool	Description	Partner	KPI(s)	Timeframe
Project communication strategy	The Communication Strategy is designed to ensure that the project effectively communicates results to the widest possible audience by using the appropriate channels and tools, targeting specific groups and key people; promotes networking and establishes a coordinated approach to maximise impact. The document provides guidelines for the implementation of communication activities right from the project start and throughout its whole lifecycle, identifies actions, tools and target groups to be addressed, depending on the project's stage of implementation, e.g., linking the communication with the task in progress.	All partners	Adoption of the document	June 2024 and regular (yearly) updates
Internal Communication Plan	The OSCARS Internal Communication Plan is intended to ensure a constant and effective exchange of information between the partners and the project's governing bodies. After its first publication, the document will be updated, if needed, throughout the project implementation phase.	CNRS, CERIC and all other partners	Adoption of the document	June 2024 and future updates, if needed
Project Identity	Design of the logo, design and development of different layouts: different templates for documents, powerpoint presentations, conference badges, etc.	Trust-IT, CERIC and all other partners	Complete set of layouts realised and adopted	January-March 2024
Project Website	Design and publication of the project's website (https://oscars-project.eu). This will be the main communication and dissemination tool used to promote project activities, disseminate results and make accessible all project public reports, services and deliverables. The website is in English. The structure is the following: Home / About / Open Calls / Services / Open Science Projects / Resources / News and Events / EOSC. Further details about the website's structure are available in D4.1 – Project Web page for central communication and dissemination purposes. The structure and content will be continuously developed and updated by Trust-IT and CERIC with contributions from all partners. The website will be accessible for 5 years after the end of the project. Relevant outputs and documents will be made available online on the Science Clusters' separate websites, as well as on www.science-clusters.eu , but also through the EOSC Association and other appropriate platforms.	Trust-IT, CERIC and all other partners	Publication of the website	January 2024 – Dec 2032
Science Clusters Websites	The five Science Clusters will inform and communicate about the OSCARS project via their own websites.	Science Clusters	Info about OSCARS and the OS projects published in the Science Clusters' website	Jan 2024 – Dec 2027

Tool	Description	Partner	KPI(s)	Timeframe
Social Media Accounts	The OSCARS X (former Twitter) account @oscars_eu and the project's LinkedIn account https://www.linkedin.com/company/oscars-project/ , as well as the social media accounts of the Science Clusters, will be used to promote OSCARS activities and Open Calls, and engage the research communities across all domains, as well as representatives from national and European institutions, ERICs and RIs, and other EOSC stakeholders. Video pills about the project and its activities will be uploaded to and distributed via the OSCARS YouTube channel at https://www.youtube.com/@OSCARS-project-EU	CERIC, Trust-IT and all other partners	At least two tweets per week published from the OSCARS X and LinkedIn accounts	Continuative
Videos	The project will produce a total of 30 short videos including 4 annual project videos, 4 animated videos, 6 video pills to promote the Open Calls for Open Science projects and services, 12 video interviews and 4 event videos for distribution through all OSCARS digital communication channels.	Trust-IT and contribution of all partners	Video published on the OSCARS website and on the project Youtube channel, and distributed via the project's communication channels	March 2024 - Dec 2027
E-newsletters	The project has developed its own newsletter, which will be distributed to subscribers every two months, or whenever relevant. Project partners and the Science Clusters will distribute the news about the project to their networks through their own e-newsletters.	CERIC and contribution of all partners	Timely release of issues	March 2024 – December 2027
Media Relations	Efforts will be made to communicate the OSCARS project in scientific/technical newspapers, business or targeted press. Articles and press releases will be published on the project's and the Science Clusters' websites, as well as distributed to the media when appropriate, to promote the project's activities and keep its stakeholders updated about latest news, events and achievements.	All partners	No. of press articles released	Continuative
Promotional Material	Design and production of the project's rollups, leaflets, give-aways (pens, conference folders, usb sticks, lanyards, etc.)	Trust-IT	Complete set of material available for OSCARS events	March 2024 and whenever relevant
Annual Communication Plan	The communication and dissemination plan of the project will be revised on a yearly basis.	CERIC, Trust-IT + contribution of all partners	Yearly delivery of the updated plan	June 2024 - Jan 2027

Tool	Description	Partner	KPI(s)	Timeframe
Reporting	OSCARS contributors in WP4, together with the Work Package Co-leaders, will provide the Coordinator with the periodical summaries specifically related to the communication and dissemination (C&D) activities carried out during each reporting period, and will be in charge of the continuous reporting on the EC Funding and Tenders Portal, for what concerns the communication and dissemination activities.	CERIC, Trust-IT, CNRS, WP leaders	Periodical summary of C&D activities delivered	Continuous,
Networking / Outreach Events (see table 6)	Promotion of the project annual event and other networking events in which OSCARS is presented (e.g., Science Clusters' and user meetings, ICRI Conference, EOSC-related events, relevant meetings of Horizon Europe projects EVERSE, EOSC Beyond, Skills4EOSC, etc.), through the social media accounts of OSCARS and the Science Clusters', together with targeted email-marketing campaigns, and the publication of the outcomes of the events on the OSCARS and the Science Clusters' websites.	All partners	Communication material released and published on available channels (website, social media, etc.)	Continuous
Promotional and info-campaigns	Targeted information campaigns (via the project's and the Science Clusters' websites, newsletters, social media, email-marketing, etc.) for the promotion of the outcomes (results, deliverables, presentations, services, tools, etc.) of OSCARS and the Open Science projects and services funded through its Open Calls.	All partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · No. of articles published on each topic; · No. of recipients of informative emails · No. of social media posts on each topic · No. of views and downloads of the published material 	After publication of deliverable / Open Science project' result
Training events and material	Support in the promotion of the training material and activities produced in the CCCs and of the summer schools organised in the frame of the project.	All partners / Science Clusters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · No. of participants · Material published 	When relevant

7. Internal Communication

Internal communication needs to be carried out taking into account two different layers of what is conceived as “internal”: one encompasses the OSCARS partnership, and the other one includes all the Science Clusters, thus a wider community of research infrastructures from the various domains.

To ensure that information flows between the different work packages (WPs), WP Leaders, the Executive Board (EB), the Science Cluster Board (SCB), and all consortium members, the project partnership holds regular meetings:

- **WP-specific bi-weekly videoconferences** with WPs’ contributors invited to give an update on the progress in the various tasks.
- **Executive Board bi-weekly videoconferences** chaired by the Project Manager and attended by the Executive Board members (WP leads and co-leads), with WP leaders invited to give an update of their area.
- **Science Cluster Board bi-weekly/monthly periodical meeting** attended by OSCARS’ project managers and the Science Clusters’ representatives, to give updates on the OSCARS’ progress and on the status and progress of consolidation and Open Call activities involving all Science Clusters.
- **OSCARS’ Annual General Meeting (AGM) annual event** attended by all consortium members, the EoB members, WP contributors, and to which specific stakeholders, and/or representatives of other EOSC projects/initiatives are invited to attend as well.

On top of these, more regular meetings are scheduled as required, to ensure that information flows between the governing bodies and WP leaders, and between different WPs. Each WP leader will be in charge of organising the communication within his/her WP contributors and stakeholders, with regular meetings (via videoconference) encouraged.

Summary notes from the meetings and reports are available in the OSCARS’ shared drive on Google, where all OSCARS’ consortium members have access, and that is the main partners’ archive and source for templates of deliverables and working documents. In addition, the consortium partnership relies on the OSCARS website’s intranet, which is accessible by OSCARS’ members only, to provide some project guidelines and links to other documents and sources of information.

Where maximum confidentiality is called for, documents are exchanged via direct email and through the online IN2P3 BOX repository hosted on the CNRS servers, dedicated solely to the project.

7.1 Mailing lists

OSCARS uses dedicated mailing lists for different audiences:

- Mailing list reaching out to all OSCARS members: all@oscars-project.eu
- Mailing lists to reach out to all OSCARS members involved in the science-related activities: all-science@oscars-project.eu
- Mailing list reaching out to all OSCARS members involved in administration activities: all-administration@oscars-project.eu
- Mailing list used for management-related issues: management@oscars-project.eu
- Executive Board mailing list (Coordinator, WP Leaders, Communication Leaders, Executive Board members and Coordinator): execboard@oscars-project.eu
- WP lists (one mailing list per WP with membership administered by the WP leader):
 - WP1: wp1@oscars-project.eu
 - WP2: wp2@oscars-project.eu
 - WP3: wp3@oscars-project.eu
 - WP4: see above management related issues wp4@oscars-project.eu
- Mailing list gathering all OSCARS members involved in communication activities: communication@oscars-project.eu
- No-reply mailing list used to send the OSCARS newsletter: noreply@oscars-project.eu
- Mailing lists for enquiries by potential applicants, about the OSCARS Open Calls:
 - opencall@oscars-project.eu - For general questions about funding rules, reporting requirements and similar and on proposals related to scientific disciplines not included in those covered by the Science Clusters
 - grantsplatform@oscars-project.eu - For enquiries about the Grants' Platform
 - envri@oscars-project.eu – For scientific questions on proposals related to ENVRI Science Cluster (Environmental Sciences)
 - escape@oscars-project.eu - For scientific questions on proposals related to the ESCAPE Science Cluster (Astronomy, Nuclear & Particle Physics)
 - lsri@oscars-project.eu – For scientific questions on proposals related to the LS RI Science Cluster (Life Sciences)
 - panosc@oscars-project.eu - For scientific questions on proposals related to the PaNOSC Science Cluster (Photon and Neutron Science)
 - sshoc@oscars-project.eu - For scientific questions on proposals related to the SSHOC Science Cluster (Social Science and Humanities)

7.2 Repositories

Working documents are stored in the OSCARS Google drive accessible to all OSCARS members, and confidential documents are stored in the online IN2P3 BOX repository hosted on the CNRS servers. Links to the repository and to confidential documents will be accessible also from the reserved area in the OSCARS website (intranet).

7.3 Internal Guidelines' for events' organisation

If a partners organises an event in the framework of OSCARS, the following rules and tips should be taken into account:

1. Inform the OSCARS communication staff via email at communication@oscars-project.eu as soon as the event has been scheduled and its scope defined.
2. Provide the OSCARS communication staff with the following information:
 - Name of the event
 - Timeframe and location
 - Event's scope
 - Target audience and key message(s)
 - Event's responsible and contact persons(s)
 - Add the event in the OSCARS Google Calendar:
<https://calendar.google.com/calendar/u/0?cid=b3NjYXJzY29tbXVuaWNhdGlvbNNAZ21haWwuY29t>
3. Inform the OSCARS communication staff about any extra need that the event may require and investigate whether the budget is available.
4. Always make reference to the project's communication strategy when communicating the project and contact the OSCARS communication staff at communication@oscars-project.eu, should you need additional material when relevant announcements must be prepared aiming at the promotion of the event through the project's website, social media, newsletters and the press. The OSCARS communication staff will provide support in preparing the key messages and materials needed.
5. Upon completion of the event, the partner has to:
 - Upload presentations and other dissemination material to the specific event's related folder in the OSCARS Google drive:
https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1mnKR-t3QTUDXWHVZz_pQsdoAFclM6HU3?usp=drive_link
 - Send them to the OSCARS communication staff to publish them on the website, social media and update the dissemination records.

- Fill in the “Continuous Reporting” excel sheet on the OSCARS Google drive at https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1J9WdB3mv5Q7e2oG1wfCuRPrYGlqqclkb/edit?usp=drive_link&oid=108162792664025256739&rtpof=true&sd=true

8. Consolidation of Science Clusters’ achievements

Collaboration and consolidation of the Science Clusters (SCs) promotes their long-term role in framing an offer to accompany, help, involve, coordinate, and empower scientists to commit to Open Science practices, to connect with EOSC, and foster the uptake of the Science Clusters’ services and solutions. OSCARS’ first objective is thus to **consolidate the achievements** from the five H2020 INFRA-EOSC-2018-01-04 projects – ESCAPE (Astronomy & Particle Physics), ENVRI-FAIR (Environment and Earth Sciences), EOSC-Life (Life Sciences), PaNOSC (Photon and Neutron science) and SSHOC (Social Science and Humanities) – **into lasting interdisciplinary services and working practices**.

The cross-fertilisation research and innovation framework that the SCs have developed and deployed within the H2020 work programme fosters consolidation towards the structural development of **Community-based Competence Centres (CCCs)**.

In this respect, one of the aims of OSCARS is to set up, within each SC, a **Cluster Open Science Competence Centre (CLOCC)**, a ‘virtual hub dedicated to fostering research excellence through training and knowledge transfer. CLOCCs are community-based initiatives supported by a collaborative network of people in the context of the Science Clusters providing expertise, best practices and services in relation to Open Science, and the promotion of cross-disciplinary collaboration’.

The concept is something new that will be deployed to leverage the specific achievements and competences of each SC, addressing each scientific community’s culture and needs, while at the same time strengthening intra-cluster collaboration by sharing best practices and jointly developing common strategies.

In this respect, the SCs have also been conducting a consolidation activity of their own composable science platforms, generally named **Composable Open Data and Analysis Services (CODAS)** where composable means the quality of components to be selected and assembled in various combinations.

The goal is to foster composability of open data and analysis services and their possible integration into the EOSC (either within some thematic, or national node), or their use in combination with EOSC services, while strengthening RI-specific and Cluster-based customisation, operation and sustainability strategies. To this aim, the SCs will further develop domain-specific and cross-cluster solutions for sharing services and methods that target FAIR data.

CODAS, which span (meta)data, workflows, tools, software and services for data discovery, data management, data transfer, data access, data analysis, simulation and training, will be accessible via cluster-specific **Virtual Research Environments (VREs)**, which are web-based operational platforms

already prototyped and deployed during the H2020 Science Clusters' projects, for further consolidation throughout the implementation of the OSCARS project.

Last but not least, dedicated resources are planned to be deployed to **engage with EOSC governance structures, as well as with EOSC-related projects and initiatives** contributing to the creation of a pan-European data access mechanism and the EOSC partnership at large, including national activities for EOSC. This will facilitate the outreach of the inter-cluster actions and the consolidation of their CCCs, enabling them to participate in the evolution of the EOSC sustainability models, or even provide continuous feedback and requirements for the overall EOSC ecosystem.

The communication and dissemination plan related to OSCARS consolidation activities, and aimed at fostering the further exploitation of the Science Clusters' services and achievements, are showcased in the following paragraphs.

8.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan

CONVEYING CLEAR MESSAGES

When communicating about the project and the consolidation activities of the Science Clusters, it will be crucial to convey clear messages and distinct definitions.

This is why a **glossary** to be compliant with metadata standards is expected to be produced and published on the OSCARS website to ensure there is a common understanding of key concepts and definitions of the vocabulary related to the EOSC, FAIR data, Open Science and Open Research practices.

PROMOTING AWARENESS, INVOLVEMENT, AND ACTIVITY OF CCCs WITHIN THE SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY AT LARGE

CCCs/CLOCCs will need a lot of communication, to make their concept and objectives easily understandable:

- What are CCCs and what is their scope?
- Who are they for?
- How can CCCs support open science / FAIR data research and data stewardship?
- Why should a researcher go to the cluster-level CC when they could go to their thematic RI?
- What is the added value of using cluster-level CCs?
- How can CCCs help with training?

Therefore, for the proper communication, promotion and monitoring of CLOCCs, a first set of actions is foreseen throughout the project implementation. These include:

- ★ Publication and promotion of CCC/CLOCC definition and description of their scope, structure and activities across the Science Clusters' RIs and their research communities, via the websites of OSCARS and the Science Clusters, social media and newsletters (of OSCARS, of

the SCs, and RIs in the SCs), as well as by presenting the concept and activities to domain-specific conferences and events (WP1, WP4).

- **Target Group:** RI experts, Researchers; Science Clusters
 - **Timing:** varying frequencies, starting May 2024.
- ★ Identification of CCCs' building blocks for the various SCs (WP1).
- **Target Group:** OSCARS members, RI experts, Researchers; Science Clusters
 - **Timing:** 2024
- ★ Identification of stakeholders in the RIs of each Science Cluster (WP1).
- **Target Group:** OSCARS members
 - **Timing:** 2024
- ★ Investigation on how to organise training/learning material (WP1).
- **Target Group:** RI Experts, Researchers, Science Clusters
- ★ Publication and promotion of training material (tutorials, howto/s) on all channels available (website, newsletters, social media, events), and organisation of hands-on training events (WP1, WP3, WP4).
- **Target Group:** RI experts, Researchers, Science Clusters
 - **Timing:** varying frequencies
- ★ Engagement with key stakeholders, the scientific communities and citizen scientists to gather user requirements for the disciplinary and cross-disciplinary scenarios of use of EOSC, via online surveys and collecting input and feedback at conferences and events (an example is the OSCARS World Café that was organised at the EOSC Association 2024 Winter School held in January 2024).
- **Target Group:** RI experts, research communities, citizen scientists
 - **Timing:** continuous
- ★ Setup of a dashboard including story steps with KPIs and maturity assessment of each CCC to monitor their performance.
- **Target Group:** OSCARS members, RI experts, Science Clusters
 - **Timing:** continuous
- ★ Publication and promotion of a position paper on CCCs/CLOCCs
- **Target Group:** RI experts, Researchers; Science Clusters, EC
 - **Timing:** 2027

PROMOTING ACCESS TO, AND FOSTERING THE USE OF CODAS

CODAS (Data Lakes, Digital Library Platforms, federated data infrastructures, remote data analysis platforms, etc.) are entry points to a wide set of computing services being continuously developed at the RIs in the Science Clusters, allowing remote access to (sensitive) data and metadata for data analysis and simulation with Jupyter Notebooks and Remote Desktops.

OSCARS' CODAS are designed to be highly composable, allowing for tailored solutions to specific research needs.

To inform and to increase the knowledge and awareness of CODAS' availability and functionalities across the research communities in and beyond the Science Clusters, and foster their use, a set of communication and dissemination actions will be carried out:

- ★ Engagement with (national) Research Infrastructures for the definition of a portfolio of FAIR data services across the Science Clusters (WP2).
 - **Target Group:** RI Experts, Researchers, Science Clusters, (national) RIs
 - **Timing:** throughout 2024

- ★ CODAS publication on RIs'/SCs' catalogues (WP2).
 - **Target Group:** RI Experts, Researchers, Science Clusters, (national) RIs
 - **Timing:** varying frequencies, starting 2025 onwards

- ★ Production, publication and promotion of training material (tutorials, howto/s) on all channels available (website, newsletters, social media, events), and organisation of hands-on training events (WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4).
 - **Target Group:** RI Experts, Researchers, Science Clusters
 - **Timing:** varying frequencies.

- ★ Identification of and engagement with Early Career Researchers (ECRs) to become RIs' influencers/ambassadors/champions on Open Science and FAIR data practices in the research communities across the SCs (WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4).
 - **Target Group:** Researchers, RIs, Science Clusters
 - **Timing:** varying frequencies / on occasion of OSCARS annual events, summer school(s), workshops, other (cluster-specific) conferences and events.

- ★ Dissemination of the outcomes of the H2020 Science Clusters' projects through the project and the SC's websites, newsletters, social media accounts (WP2, WP4).
 - **Target Group:** Researchers
 - **Timing:** continuous, various frequencies until end of project.

- ★ Publication and dissemination of (scientific) articles on the use and benefits of cluster-specific CODAS (WP2, WP4).
 - **Target Group:** Researchers
 - **Timing:** when new developments are available. Various frequencies until the end of the project

- ★ Development, publication and dissemination of demos and use cases to facilitate the use of CODAS through OSCARS' and the SCs' digital channels and newsletters (WP2, WP4).
 - **Target Group:** Researchers
 - **Timing:** when new developments are available. Various frequencies until the end of the project.

- ★ Direct engagement with scientific communities under Task 2.3 (“Engagement”). Each community will present their work through 1–2 exemplar demonstrators, with each of the clusters identifying the best strategy based on the selected demonstrators.
 - **Target Group:** Researchers
 - **Timing:** as the demonstrators achieve sufficient maturity, towards the end of the project.

COOPERATING WITH INTERNATIONAL FORA, AND WITH EOSC- AND RI DEVELOPMENT-RELATED PROJECTS

In the frame of WP3 and in collaboration with the other WPs, OSCARS aims at engaging with existing networks, projects, international fora and working groups towards the setup of a European data steward registry to network and share competences, knowledge and best practices on FAIR data, Open Science and data management practices. Collaboration is also aimed at setting up a dashboard model for Competence Centers and their related activities, as well as a mentoring strategy to help disseminate skills and good practices within and across CCCs.

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

It is important to target messages according to the stakeholder type the project will communicate to. Thus, a careful **stakeholder analysis** is foreseen to ensure all audiences are taken into consideration at an adequate level of granularity, also leveraging on the previous work carried out in the frame of the H2020 Science Cluster projects.

MAKING OSCARS’ DELIVERABLES EASILY ACCESSIBLE AND PUBLICLY AVAILABLE

As foreseen by OSCARS Data Management Plan, all OSCARS deliverables and blueprints will be uploaded in the OSCARS community on Zenodo - <https://zenodo.org/communities/oscars/>, and will thus be accessible via a DOI. Other documents and resources, such as presentations, videos, guidelines, etc. will be accessible from the “Resources” section on the OSCARS website - <https://oscars-project.eu/resources>, offering filtering by year and by document type.

8.2 Exploitation Plan

Within the H2020 work programme, the Science Clusters have successfully initiated the transformation of the way researchers create, share and exploit research data, protocols, methodologies and software across large research disciplines, in some cases bridging traditional cultural barriers against cooperation. It is essential that the OSCARS consolidation action targets both the continuous support to services and methodologies aimed at such a transformation, as well as securing their operational sustainability. The OSCARS consortium is expecting that these achievements will result in better quality, more innovation and higher productivity of research.

PROMOTING THE ADOPTION OF FAIR DATA AND OPEN SCIENCE PRACTICES THROUGH CCCs

It is expected that, following the setup of CCCs, and throughout their implementation, both during and after OSCARS, CCCs will:

- ★ Increase data and metadata FAIRness, interoperability and re-use of scientific data and products.
 - **Action:** CCCs will create new collaborations with scientific communities and publishers for promoting standard metadata and automatic verification before publication to ensure their FAIRness, encouraging the increase in the quality of metadata and thus enhancing the findability of the data and supporting its reuse.
 - **Beneficiaries:** RIs, scientific communities / researchers, citizen scientists, publishers.

- ★ Improve robustness of data management and curation protocols.
 - **Action:** Update of DMPs and of data management and curation protocols, by defining a comprehensive set of practices and principles that ensure the proper management of data assets at the RIs in the Science Clusters, ensuring data security and protection, as well as data quality, accessibility and, more generally, data FAIRness.
 - **Beneficiaries:** data managers, RIs, scientific communities / researchers.

- ★ Raise awareness and implementation of Open Science workflows.
 - **Action:** Share use cases and demonstrators among the Science Clusters' research communities, stimulating the adoption of Open Science and Open Research practices.
 - **Beneficiaries:** RIs, scientific communities / researchers, citizen scientists.

- ★ Provide access to research outputs.
 - **Action:** Make research outputs findable and accessible via cluster-based Virtual Research Environments and provide assistance at the CCCs' level.
 - **Beneficiaries:** RIs, scientific communities / researchers, industry (incl. SMEs), citizen scientists.

- ★ Support/assist emerging RIs in the evaluation and further development of technologies, software, open-source code, repositories, new generation research workspaces (cloud, FAIR, VRE).
 - **Action:** produce and provide guidelines, including methodology for assessing and improving the FAIRness and quality of offered resources, howto/s on composability, best practices, etc.).
 - **Beneficiaries:** (new) RIs.

- ★ Provide expert advice and training on FAIR data policies, FAIR data catalogues, adoption of metadata standards, data formats, data curation and Data Management Plans.
 - **Action:** Make training resources available and easily findable and accessible through the channels of OSCARS and the Science Clusters, and promote them to key

stakeholders. CCCs will have their own webpage in the websites of the Science Clusters, with links to training resources, relevant use cases and presentations of key results, webinars and videos showcasing best practices, as well as contact information to ask for advice from CCCs' experts.

- **Beneficiaries:** RIs, data stewards, scientific communities, (young) researchers / PhD students, universities industry (incl. SMEs), citizen scientists.

In the following section, the main Key Exploitable Results (KERs)² are presented.

KER: White papers on CCCs

Description: To promote and support their further exploitation by RIs in the Science Clusters, and by their research communities, each CCC will produce a white paper, or peer-reviewed papers which will be accessible via a DOI from Zenodo and from the OSCARS and the related Science Cluster website. It will include the plan for further exploitation of the services offered within each CCC, and might be supported by a video presenting the key results.

Result Type: White paper.

Key Innovation: CCCs as reference points by RIs/ERICs in the Science Clusters for training and advice on FAIR data and Open Science.

Stakeholders: Researchers, (e-)RIs/ERICs	
Benefits	The RIs in the Science Clusters will agree on CCCs' role, challenges and key activities and further benefit from the definition of their missions within them to define their future strategy and work plan with reference to FAIR data and Open Science.
Dissemination	Publication on Zenodo, on the OSCARS and the Science Clusters' websites, social media and newsletters, and websites of the RIs in the CCC.
Exploitation path	<p>Adoption and further Exploitation of CCCs</p> <p>The white papers will set a common basis for the RIs in the Community-based Competence Centres to continue their activity even after the end of OSCARS, to serve the research communities in the Science Clusters with training and mentoring resources and services, and encourage the use of the tools, resources and services developed by the Science Clusters.</p>

KER: Registry of CCCs' members

Description: Each Science Cluster' CCC will create a registry including its members and data stewards,

² KER definition from the [Horizon Results Platform | Intellectual Property Helpdesk](#) - A Key Exploitable Result (KER) is an identified main interesting result, which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be "exploited" – meaning to make use and derive benefits- downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education. In order for you to select and prioritise your results, we would recommend that you use the following criteria: degree of innovation, exploitability and impact.

which will be accessible from the OSCARS website, with competences' tags and information about competences and involvement in other projects. The idea behind this type of registry is to provide a platform to each CCC's members (incl. data stewards) to network and exchange knowledge and best practices. The registries will be accessible from the websites of the Science Clusters, while the www.science-clusters.eu website will offer a single access point to the registries of all the five Science Clusters.

Result Type: Registry

Key Innovation: Networking tool to find competences in the CCCs on data stewardship, FAIR data management, Open Science, and more.

Stakeholders: Researchers, (e-)RIs/ERICs	
Benefits	Exchange knowledge and best practices in the SCs among RIs' professionals and experts in FAIR data, Open Science, data stewardship, and more.
Dissemination	OSCARS website, Science Clusters' websites.
Exploitation path	Networking and Knowledge Transfer The CCCs' registries will allow RIs' professionals and data stewards to increase their knowledge to better serve the research communities across the Science Clusters to adopt FAIR data and Open Science practices, providing their competences and advice.

STIMULATING THE USE AND FURTHER EXPLOITATION OF CODAS

Successful exploitation implies turning scientific results and prototypes into sustainable, user-optimised, ready-for-use applications and services. To this aim, a set of actions is foreseen to stimulate the use and further exploitation of CODAS:

- ★ Making composable services and workflows (also through the publication of use cases and science demonstrators) known to / findable by potential users, through the www.science-clusters.eu website, as well as through the websites of the Science Clusters / CCCs.
 - **Beneficiaries:** Data scientists, Researchers, Science Clusters, Citizen scientists, Industry (incl. SMEs).
 - **Timing:** when services are ready, tested and deployed.

- ★ 2-3 engagement workshops will be organised by the Clusters to demonstrate the benefits of service and data composability to a wide variety of research communities.
 - **Beneficiaries:** RI Experts, Data scientists, Researchers, Science Clusters, Citizen scientists, Industry (incl. SMEs).
 - **Timing:** when services are ready, tested and deployed.

- ★ Publication, in the VREs, of reproducible research workflows, with PiD for each "component"

used, e.g. datasets, tools, software, etc.).

- **Beneficiaries:** RI Experts, Data scientists, Researchers, Science Clusters, Citizen scientists, Industry (incl. SMEs).
- **Timing:** when a new workflow is published.

KER: CODAS use cases and demonstrators

Description: Use cases and science demonstrators highlight the benefits of service composability and engage researchers in order to encourage uptake and solicit feedback. For example, documenting and publishing a research process; converting such documentation into a machine-actionable and reproducible workflow; building and using a federated storage service and analysing DOI-identified data from multiple repositories. These demonstrators are intended to document community best practice. They also offer starting points, or inspiration for future work (for example, the Cascading grant projects in WP4) and collaborations, for example sectoral data spaces (e.g. language, cultural heritage, health, etc.).

Result Type: Use cases / science demonstrators

Key Innovation: Increased accessibility and use, by the scientific community at large, of the composable services in the Science Clusters.

Stakeholders: RI Experts, Data scientists, Researchers, Science Clusters, Industry (incl. SMEs)	
Benefits	Increased knowledge about CODAS and increased findability and use by the scientific community at large, as well as by citizen scientists, industry, (e-)RIs / ERICs and international research organisations.
Dissemination	Publication and promotion of the use cases and demonstrators on Zenodo, on the OSCARS, the separate Science Clusters' websites, and on www.science-clusters.eu , newsletters, social media accounts. Production of demos and videos, and presentation at scientific and/or cluster-specific conferences and events.
Exploitation path	Uptake of Open Science and Open Research practices By showcasing best practices through use cases and science demonstrators, foster the uptake of a similar Open Science and Open Research approach in the research communities across and beyond the Science Clusters, and improve trust in science by encouraging citizens and industries to take up open data.

The Exploitation Plan will be further developed within the work packages in collaboration with the participating partners. We will also request the project partners and the Science Clusters to exploit these results and provide necessary feedback.

Furthermore, depending on the Science Clusters' services considered, the results might be exploited at different levels: Go-to-Market Strategy, Scientific Exploitation, Commercial Exploitation, or Open Source Exploitation. Such classification will be explored throughout the project implementation and considered in a later version of this document.

9. Open Calls for Open Science projects and services

OSCARS' second key objective is to lead and foster the involvement of a broad range of research communities in EOSC via the development of new Open Science projects and services, that together will **drive the uptake of FAIR-data-intensive research throughout the European Research Area (ERA)**.

The two **OSCARS Open Calls for Open Science projects and services**, to be implemented through a cascading-grant mechanism, are expected to enable and facilitate new achievements in basic research, and solutions in key application areas. This will demonstrate that the Science Clusters have been able to bring scientific content into EOSC, and so to enable its successful operational phase.

However, there is an even higher impact to be expected. Building on the progress already achieved, the FAIR research data (developed and/or deployed by the Science Clusters), in particular the data-platforms that participate in the expected EOSC "Web of FAIR Data and Services" for Science, will contribute to the creation of a **data space for science** together with the other data spaces within the European Strategy for Data.

Moreover, OSCARS will contribute to networking competences, training, mentoring Open Science projects and emerging RIs, and adopting together, after evaluation, seamless services and technology for the FAIR management of scientific results and all associated digital objects. A particular attention will be reserved for relevant datasets from RIs, the innovative software and services for interoperability, and legacy of data.

The OSCARS Open Calls should guarantee that the impact will be even bigger by encouraging citizens and industries to take up open data (improving trust in science).

The related communication and dissemination activities, as well as those foreseen to foster the exploitation of the results of the funded Open Science projects and services, are showcased in the following paragraphs.

9.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan

PROMOTING THE OSCARS OPEN CALLS TO THE RESEARCH COMMUNITIES IN THE SCIENCE CLUSTERS AND BEYOND

For the promotion of the OSCARS Open Calls for Open Science project and services, it is crucial to clearly define the following:

- What is the scope of the Open Calls?
- What are Open Science projects and services?
- Who are the Open Calls for?
- What are the eligibility criteria?
- Information about Open Science projects' funding, duration and application deadlines.

- What are the expected deliverables of the Open Science projects?
- Where/how to apply?

For the proper communication and promotion of the OSCARS Open Calls, a set of actions has been foreseen during the first year of the project. These include:

- ★ Setup and publication of a webpage on the OSCARS website, with the information about the Open Calls as listed above:
 - **Target group:** researchers / research communities from the Science Clusters and beyond, RIs / ERICs, industry (incl. SMEs), citizen scientists, NCPs for Research Infrastructures, EOSC Association
 - **Timing:** before the launch of the Open Calls, i.e. ready by 15th March 2024, and by mid-November 2024.
- ★ Collection and publication on the OSCARS website, of a selection of Open Science projects' examples already implemented by the Science Clusters in the frame of the Horizon 2020 projects (ENVRI, EOSC-Life, ESCAPE, PaNOSC, SSHOC) and promotion via the media channels of OSCARS and the Science Clusters (website, social media, newsletters), as well as at the Open Calls' launch events, and other relevant conferences and events.
 - **Target group:** potential applicants to the Open Calls: researchers from all scientific domains, industry / SMEs, international organisations, PhD students, RIs, universities.
 - **Timing:** before the launch of the Open Calls, i.e. ready by 15th March 2024, and by mid November 2024.
- ★ Organisation and promotion of two Open Calls' launch events open to the public, with a live Q&A session to reply to the questions from potential applicants.
 - **Target group:** potential applicants to the Open Calls: researchers from all scientific domains, industry / SMEs, international organisations, PhD students, RIs, universities.
 - **Timing:** day of launch of the Open Calls, i.e. 15th March 2024, and mid November 2024.
- ★ Publication of a FAQs section on the OSCARS website, to make publicly available and easily accessible the answers to the frequently asked questions coming from potential applicants, both at the Open Calls' launch events and at the "Ask me anything" sessions, and via the mailing lists set up for the Open Calls.
 - **Target group:** potential applicants to the Open Calls: researchers from all scientific domains, industry / SMEs, international organisations, PhD students, RIs, universities.
 - **Timing:** ready from the day of launch of the Open Calls, i.e. 15th March 2024, and mid November 2024, and continuously updated with answers to questions coming via mail to the mailing lists dedicated to the Open Calls, and through the dedicated Q&A online sessions.

- ★ Publication and promotion of the recordings and presentations of the Open Call launch events, as well as of the video interviews presenting the Open Calls, on the OSCARS website and via the project's and the Science Clusters' social media channels and newsletters.
 - **Target group:** potential applicants to the Open Calls: researchers from all scientific domains, industry / SMEs, international organisations, PhD students, RIs, universities.
 - **Timing:** right after the Open Calls' launch events: March 2024 and November 2024.

- ★ Organisation and promotion of "Ask me anything" online sessions for potential applicants to ask their questions live and get their answers on the Open Calls from the OSCARS project manager and Science Clusters' representatives, and publication of the answers in the FAQs' section of the OSCARS website.
 - **Target group:** potential applicants to the Open Calls (researchers from all scientific domains, industry / SMEs, international organisations, PhD students, RIs, universities), RIs' representatives, NCPs.
 - **Timing:** right after the Open Calls' launch events: April-May2024 and November-January 2024.

- ★ Advertisement of the statistics from the OSCARS Open Calls via the OSCARS and the Science Clusters' websites, social media and newsletters, to showcase success, and think about possible future adjustments.
 - **Target group:** potential applicants to the Open Calls (researchers from all scientific domains, industry / SMEs, international organisations, PhD students, RIs, universities), RIs, Science Clusters, EC, EOSC Association.
 - **Timing:** right after the Open Calls' closure dates: May 2024 and January 2025.

- ★ Setup and operation of the Grants' Platform to apply to the OSCARS Open Calls' and manage the evaluation of proposals.
 - **Target group:** potential applicants to the Open Calls (researchers from all scientific domains, industry / SMEs, international organisations, PhD students, RIs, universities), evaluators, Science Clusters.
 - **Timing:** Before the Open Calls' launch. March 2024 and November 2024.

- ★ Information and communication on how to use the Grants' Platform via a video tutorial published on the OSCARS' website and Youtube channel, and via the "Ask me anything" online sessions.
 - **Target group:** potential applicants to the Open Calls: researchers from all scientific domains, industry / SMEs, international organisations, PhD students, RIs, universities.
 - **Timing:** right after the Open Calls' launch. March 2024 and November 2024.

- ★ Publication of the information about the Open Science projects and services funded using the summaries and names provided by each project's PI, on the OSCARS website, and distribution of the information via the OSCARS social media channels and newsletters.
 - **Target group:** researchers from all scientific domains, industry / SMEs, international

- organisations, PhD students, RIs, universities, Science Clusters, RIs/ERICs, EC.
- **Timing:** right after the selection and TPPA signature of the funded Open Science projects.
- ★ Production and distribution of print materials about OSCARS Open Calls at conferences and events.
 - **Target group:** researchers from all scientific domains, industry / SMEs, international organisations, PhD students, RIs, universities, Science Clusters, RIs/ERICs, other EOSC projects and initiatives, EC.
 - **Timing:** before the Open Calls are closed (2024, until January 2025).

DISSEMINATING THE RESULTS OF THE SUCCESSFUL OPEN SCIENCE PROJECTS AND SERVICES

To disseminate the results of the funded Open Science projects with the goal of maximising their impact and fostering the uptake of Open Science and Open Research practices by the research communities in and beyond the Science Clusters, a set of dissemination actions is foreseen once the projects' results will be available:

- ★ Production and publication of news posts and/or press releases about the results of the successful Open Science projects and services, and dissemination through the OSCARS' and the Science Clusters' social media accounts and newsletters, using the information provided by the projects' PI in the final projects' summaries, presentations and scientific articles.
 - **Target group:** researchers from all scientific domains, specific research communities, industry / SMEs, international organisations, PhD students, RIs, universities, Science Clusters, RIs/ERICs, EC.
 - **Timing:** when results are available.
- ★ Present the results of the successful Open Science projects and services at cluster-specific and other scientific conferences and events.
 - **Target group:** researchers from all scientific domains, specific research communities, industry / SMEs, international organisations, PhD students, RIs, universities, Science Clusters, RIs/ERICs, EC.
 - **Timing:** when results are available.
- ★ Presentation of the achievements of the successful Open Science projects at the Summer School(s) organised in the frame of OSCARS and/or by the Science Clusters.
 - **Target group:** researchers from all scientific domains, specific research communities, industry / SMEs, international organisations, PhD students, RIs, universities, Science Clusters, RIs/ERICs.
 - **Timing:** when results are available / when a Summer School is organised.
- ★ Organisation of the OSCARS final event, to present the achievements of the successful Open Science projects and services, and dissemination of their outcomes through all OSCARS digital channels available (OSCARS websites, mailing lists, newsletter, social media, news

posts).

- **Target group:** researchers from all scientific domains, specific research communities, industry / SMEs, international organisations, PhD students, RIs, universities, Science Clusters, RIs/ERICs, EC, other EOSC projects and initiatives, EC.
 - **Timing:** OSCARS final event.
- ★ Publication of the results of the successful Open Science projects and services in peer-reviewed open access journal articles.
- **Target group:** researchers from all scientific domains, specific research communities, industry / SMEs, international organisations, PhD students, RIs, universities, Science Clusters, RIs/ERICs.
 - **Timing:** when results are available.
- ★ Publication and presentation of use cases / science demonstrators, success and implementation stories from the successful Open Science projects, on the OSCARS website, at scientific conferences and events, and dissemination via the OSCARS' and the Science Clusters' social media channels and newsletters.
- **Target group:** researchers from all scientific domains, specific research communities, industry / SMEs, international organisations, PhD students, RIs, universities, Science Clusters, RIs/ERICs, other EOSC projects and initiatives.
 - **Timing:** when results are available.
- ★ Production, and later publication on the OSCARS website and on its Youtube channel, of video interviews with PIs of a selection of successful Open Science projects, acting as Open Science ambassadors to promote the uptake of Open Science and Open Research practices by the broader research communities, and dissemination of the interview via the OSCARS' and the Science Clusters' social media channels and newsletters.
- **Target group:** researchers from all scientific domains, specific research communities, industry / SMEs, international organisations, PhD students, RIs, universities, Science Clusters, RIs/ERICs, other EOSC projects and initiatives, EC.
 - **Timing:** when results are available.

9.2 Exploitation Plan

OSCARS Open Science projects will produce results (i.e., data, services, workflows, or networks), in the scientific disciplines covered by, and beyond the Science Clusters, that will bring innovation and benefits to stakeholders.

Below are the key exploitable results (KERs) and possible exploitation paths.

KER: FAIR (meta) data, software, tools, workflows

Description: Open Science projects will make (meta)data, software, tools and/or workflows FAIR and available to fellow researchers and the general public, to facilitate accessibility and reuse by the scientific community at large, as well as by the industry, citizen scientists, and more..

Result Type: FAIR (meta)data, software, tools and/or workflows / scientific publications.

Key Innovation: Increased accessibility and reuse, by the scientific community at large, of scientific data, workflows and/or services for scientific analysis.

Stakeholders: Researchers, (e-) RIs / ERICs, industry, citizens scientists, international organisations	
Benefits	Reusability of the (meta)data, software, tools and/or workflows by the scientific community at large, as well as by citizen scientists, industry and international research organisations.
Dissemination	OSCARS final event, presentations at conferences and events, publication of success stories, use cases and science demonstrators, publication of scientific articles in peer-reviewed journals, and of news posts on OSCARS and the Science Clusters' websites, social media and newsletters.
Exploitation path	<p>Use of produced (meta)data, software, tools and/or workflows Encourage usage of produced (meta)data, software, tools and workflows, by researchers, citizen scientists, research institutions, and industry.</p> <p>Uptake of Open Science and Open Research practices By showcasing best practices through use cases and science demonstrators, foster the uptake of a similar Open Science and Open Research approach in the research communities across and beyond the Science Clusters, and improve trust in science by encouraging citizens and industries to take up open data.</p>

KER: Procedure for the implementation of Cascading-grant Open Calls

Description: Procedure describing the cascading-grant Open Calls' setup, implementation process and results (what went well, what hasn't).

Result Type: Procedure / Methodology.

Key Innovation: Tested procedure for next cascading-grant Open Calls, or for a permanent approach in the European framework.

Stakeholders: Science Clusters, (e-)RIs / ERICs in the SCs, EC, other EOSC projects and initiatives	
Benefits	Availability of an already tested procedure proving the success of cascading grants for steering Open Science, for the implementation of similar Open Calls for Open Science projects and services in the future, to further contribute to the implementation of the EOSC.
Dissemination	Publication on Zenodo and on the websites of OSCARS and the Science Clusters, presentations at conferences and events.
Exploitation path	<p>Knowledge transfer and adoption</p> <p>OSCARS will share the procedure and the best practices adopted for the setup and implementation of its cascading-grant Open Calls, which can be used as a model in the future in the frame of similar projects. The Science Clusters, and the (e-)RIs/ERICs which are members of the SCs, can use such a procedure as a consolidation tool for their long-term perspective, and as a legacy to fund Open Science and Open Research projects and services in the future.</p>

KER: Training material on FAIR data and Open Science

Description: Production and publication of training material on FAIR data and Open Science.

Result Type: Training material (webinars, video demos, presentations, training modules).

Key Innovation: Train people in RIs and academic organisations on the topics of FAIR data and Open Science towards the wider adoption of Open Science and Open Research practices.

Stakeholders: researchers, (e-)RIs / ERICs, Science Clusters, other EOSC projects and initiatives	
Benefits	Increased availability of training resources for usage at RIs / ERICs, as well as at academic institutions towards an increased knowledge on FAIR data and Open Science across (early-stage) researchers in all scientific disciplines.
Dissemination	Publication on the Science Clusters' training catalogue, training events / workshops / webinars involving the research communities in all Science Clusters (and beyond).
Exploitation path	<p>Use of training resources</p> <p>Training resources can be useful tools for (e-)RIs/ERICs which are members in the Science Clusters, to train their scientific and technical staff on FAIR data and Open Science, as well as for academic institutions to train students and early-stage researchers on these topics.</p>

10. Resources

The resources available for communication, dissemination and exploitation activities in WP4 include 57.8 person months shared between CERIC, Trust-IT and COMMpla for the whole duration of the project. Those resources will be used for the design, realisation and maintenance of the project's website and the grants platform, for the realisation of the visual identity and communication/promotional material, for the payment of conferences and workshops fees, for open access publications, and any other activity linked to the communication and dissemination objectives of the WP. Changes may be introduced depending on the specific requirements of the work packages.

11. IPR Policy

OSCARS will produce a wide variety of materials, including presentations, videos, documentation, deliverables, reports, scientific data, software packages and source code. The OSCARS management of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) strongly favours wide dissemination, open access, and reuse (academic and commercial) of the project's results.

OSCARS will apply an IPR policy in the project that manages the IP generated within the project, and also includes reserving the rights generated by vesting ownership in the corporate project participants. The Consortium Agreement between the partners manages all IPR issues in line with the EC guidelines on the management of IPR, as referred to in Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council.

Whenever possible OSCARS adopts the following licence for results:

Creative Commons attribution licence CC BY 4.0 for documents, reports, presentations etc., unless otherwise agreed and for justified reasons. This allows sharing and adaptation of material as long as the work is appropriately attributed, a link is provided to the licence and any changes have been clearly indicated.

The material will be included in an appropriate public service (e.g. YouTube) or repository (OpenAIRE, or the repositories of the Science Clusters).

For results that are software:

- The software generated by the project will be released under Open Source licence conditions. We will encourage to release software, whenever possible, under the MIT, the general public licence GNU, or the Apache 2.0 licences.
- The material will be accessible through the OSCARS website, as well as through www.science-clusters.eu, and through the software catalogues of the Science Clusters.
- Any publications resulting from the project will be open access.

This policy will ensure that the widest possible audience is aware of the OSCARS achievements and that they can build on them in the future.

Abbreviations

CCC	Community-based Competence Centres
CLOCC	CLuster Open science Competence Centres
CODAS	Composable Open Data and Analysis Services
Cluster Coordinators	Representatives of the clusters, initially coordinators of the cluster projects, after the end of the projects the elected chairs, directors or other representatives of the clusters
COSP	Cross-Cluster Open Science Projects
CRISE	Composable Research Infrastructure Services in EOSC
Data Lake	ESCAPE Data Management service for Open Science
DMP	Data Management Plan
ENVRI	Environmental Research Infrastructures Cluster
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
ESCAPE	Astronomy and Particle Physics Research Infrastructures cluster
IEC	Independent Evaluation Committee
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Results
LS RIs	European Life Sciences Research Infrastructures
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
O-EB	OSCARS Executive Board
O-GA	OSCARS General Assembly
O-MST	OSCARS Management Support Team
PMB	Project Management Board
O-SCB	OSCARS Steering Board composed of the five Science Cluster Coordinators
O-TPPA	OSCARS Third-Party Project Agreements
OSCARS	Open Science Cluster's Action for Research & Society

OSP	Open Science Projects
OSPS	Open Science Projects and Services
PaN	Photon and Neutron sources in Europe
PaNOSC	Photon and Neutron Open Science Cluster
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cluster
VRE	Virtual Research Environment